

PATTERNS OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF STREET CHILDREN IN DISTRICT SOUTH KARACHI

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Abstract

This paper to identify the patterns of delinquency among street children associated factors in District South Karachi. A quantitative study was conducted using a self-developed questionnaire for face-to-face interview to collect primary data from a sample of 72 street children. The study examined various patterns contributing to delinquent behavior among street children within the local context.

This targets the patterns of delinquency among street children in District South Karachi, chosen due to the lack of previous research, and the rising ratio of street children. A strict adherence to ethical principles was maintained, including getting verbal consent, maintaining participant confidentially, allowing withdrawal at any moment, and conducting interviews in a polite and friendly manner on voluntarily basis.

The findings revealed that the largest proportion of respondents (34.7%) was aged 13-15 years, with 58.3% identifying as male. In terms of education, 27.8% had a Primary school qualification, while 27.7% had no formal education. A significant 62.5% faced challenges in accessing education, primarily due to financial difficulties (55.6%). Regarding their activities, 30.6% engaged in begging, and 15.3% were involved in illegal activities.

Family backgrounds indicated that 41.7% of respondents had jobless fathers, and 34.7% reported family incomes between 16,000 and 25,000 PKR. Most respondents (58.3%) had 4-5 family members. Notably, 41.7% left home due to poverty, with 34.7% indicating they left at ages 11-13. The majority (98.6%) had skills before leaving home, with cooking skills being the most common (21.4%).

INTRODUCTION

A street child is a child who was without family support and care and lives on a city's streets. The majority of homeless children were between the ages of five and seventeen and their numbers vary greatly throughout cities.

The word "delinquency word" has no any specific definition, but delinquency means wrong activity like,

break the rules and regulations of state or violations of social norms made by civilized citizens. It was also understood that street children were individuals who were without a home and reside in parks, streets, train yards, walkways, and shrines because they were destitute, alone, and without social support. There was not enough safety for them. The fact that some

of these children were homeless makes them high-risk. Street children's delinquent behavior exacerbated their precarious circumstances. Delinquent behavior among adolescents on the streets was a product of cultural norms and ideals of the deviant subculture. The social, economic, and environmental challenges faced by street children in District South Karachi and making their lives difficult. This district was one of the most populated and economically disparate in Karachi.

According to UNICEF's (2012) assessment, street children are boys and girls under the age of eighteen who have made the street their home and means of subsistence while receiving insufficient protection or supervision. To put it briefly, Street girls are young women who live, work, and sometimes even work as prostitutes on the streets. Of the estimated 400,000 street children in Bangladesh, about 10% have been forced into prostitution in order to survive. It is reasonable to presume that a large number of these kids are homeless girls. From the standpoint of human rights, street girls are completely shut out of the recognized rights of all people (Mozdalifa 2012).

It should be recognized that every child who lived and works on the streets has their own distinct experiences, and that the term "street children" is a social construct—despite the fact that it was still frequently employed as a handy shorthand. Most of the time, delinquent behavior was committed by street kids without their knowledge. Young people were primarily used by a delinquent group operating in the background to force them to perform crimes. The purpose of this study was to improve our understanding of the criminal behavior that was common among Bangladeshi street children. Politicians, scholars, intellectuals, and anyone focused on figuring out a path out of this risky situation could also gain insight from it. Because it was one of the most important issues, researchers from both domestic and foreign universities continue to focus on street children. Delinquency was a broad term with many nuances of meaning. It was also difficult. There was not a single similar idea regarding it. It had varied connotations in different countries and communities. Once more, the legal and moral definitions of delinquency were very different. Additionally, it took on several interpretations depending on one's social, cultural,

religious, and psychological viewpoint. It was frequently used to denote a crime that a minor had committed. Depending on the society, this crime had taken on distinct characteristics. Under their unique legal systems, several countries had varied age restrictions for delinquents.

The unfortunate ones were the street children. Children who, for the most of time lived in the streets of cities with other homeless children or were constantly on the move and had only sporadic contact with their parents or other family members (typically their mothers or sisters). A youngster might leave the house for a variety of reasons. They may have been forced to flee their home because of ongoing abuse, found themselves on the streets from the start due to family issues, or been abandoned by their parents or other relatives. People who come from terrible or traumatic homes. They dealt with family issues that they were unable to resolve, such as alcoholism, child abuse, mistreatment by stepparents, poverty, and unemployment. They had had to make the difficult decision to part ways with their family because their tolerance had been greatly exceeded.

Operational Definition

The terms "street children" refers to children who worked or live on the streets, frequently without access to basic requirements and secure housing. They might work in different jobs or turn to begging in order to make ends meet.

Street children's delinquent patterns comprised a variety of actions, such as criminal or antisocial behavior, and were usually fueled by the particular socioeconomic and environmental difficulties they face.

A state in which one had not completed enough formal education or reached the maximum level of education possible (no high school diploma, incomplete secondary education, etc.). Low reading and numeracy abilities, as determined by literacy evaluations or standardized tests, may fall under this category.

The lack of basic facilities, assistance, and required resources for learning and development. This included a shortage of skilled teachers, restricted extracurricular activities, inadequate finance for schools, and limited access to educational resources (books and technology). Measured used

questionnaires that evaluate the resources that were available in learning environments.

A state of socioeconomic hardship characterized by a lack of funds for necessities such as food, housing, and education. This could be quantified in terms of income levels (below the poverty line, for example) and evaluated using metrics including household income, social assistance accessibility, and the capacity to pay for school-related costs.

The pressure from peers to adopted particular attitudes, behaviors, or values, especially while they were teenagers or young adults. Self-reported surveys that gauge people's opinions of peer influenced on their social, intellectual, and drug usage habits as well as their actual behavioral shifts in reaction to peer dynamics could be used to quantify this.

"Pathways to delinquency for street children in China: Institutional anomie, resilience, and crime," a 2019 study by Yu, GAO, and Sheppard, explores how Chinese street children end up involved in criminal activities. In order to look towards the process that caused these 40 Kunming street kids to get involved in crime, they conducted interviews with them. The three stages that these kids go through to get involved in delinquent activities are discovered by the researcher. This study examines how, in their early years, the children were not accustomed to living on the streets and lacked street skills, which is consistent with the finding that street children were more likely to rely on unofficial survival techniques in order to obtain food or money when they lacked independent living skills. According to the study, homeless kids could.

The Bangladesh Institute of Development estimates that the nation is home to 1.5 million street children. According to The Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS), that number is anticipated to rise considerably. Two types of street children have been identified: those who labor on the streets but spend the night with their families, and as well as those who sleep on the streets. For most of their lives, street children are dependent on begging, vehicle and shop washing, unpaid labor, scavenging, engaging in delinquent behavior, etc. to make ends meet. These street kids were also involved in drug sales, gun possession, robberies, murders, acts of political violence, etc. Information dissemination to intellectuals, academics, politicians, and others who are focusing their attention on finding a solution to this perilous situation is the primary goal of this study.

"Process of Delinquent Criminalizing Street Children in Bangladesh: An Empirical Study in the city of Dhaka" by Sharmin and Disha (2021) examines the decriminalization process for street children in Dhaka. Although the delinquent behavior of street children is not new in Bangladesh, it has been significantly growing recently. The motives and effects of a single street youngster participating in these structured delinquent behaviors are covered here. Non-probability sampling and a quantitative technique were used in this study to choose participants. It draws attention to the reality that most street children commit crimes as a result of their circumstances and other people's influence.

Theoretical Framework

VARIABLES	THERIOES	REFERENCES
i. Lack Of Education	i. Socioeconomic Theory (Adam Smith 1776)	Nisar M, Ullah S, Ali M, Alam S. 2015. Juvenile Delinquency: The Influence of Family, Peer and Economic Factors on Juvenile Delinquents. Scientia Agricultural
i. Lack Of Resources	ii. Psychological Theory (Sigmund Freud 1905) i. Social Disorganization	Nisar M, Ullah S, Ali M, Alam S. 2015. Juvenile Delinquency: The Influence of Family, Peer and Economic Factors on Juvenile Delinquents. Scientia Agricultural

	Theory (Clifford Shaw 1942) ii. Strain Theory (Robert Merton 1938)	Saeed, Muhammad & Khushhal, Asif & Zahid, Muhammad. (2021). A case study of District Jail Mardan was conducted to examine the opinions of juveniles regarding the socioeconomic factors that contribute to juvenile delinquency in Pakistan. 12. 98-121.
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VARIABLES	THERIOES	REFERENCES
Poverty	i. Culture of Poverty Theory (Oscar Lewis 1966) ii. Behavioral Theory (Richard H.Thaler 2015)	Icily, T., & Çoban, S. (2012). A study on how juvenile misbehavior is influenced by friends and family in Turkey. 02(01), 66-72 in Advances in Applied Sociology. https://doi.org/10.4236/aasoci.2012.21009 .
Peer Pressure	i. Differential Association Theory (Edwin Sutherland 1939) ii. Sub-cultural Theory (Abler Cohen 1972)	Nisar M, Ullah S, Ali M, Alam S. 2015. Juvenile Delinquency: The Influence of Family, Peer and Economic Factors on Juvenile Delinquents. Scientific Agriculturists.

The lack of education refers to the scarcity of sources to, or lack of opportunities for formal schooling and leaning activities. It can lead to various factors include, educational infrastructure, cultural norms, poverty and economic barriers.

The socio economic theory has introduced by Adam Smith in 1776. This theory describes that There can be less available educational facilities as compare than stable socioeconomic backgrounds. And need to prioritize work over the schooling.

The World Bank has researched in 2018 that 20% of households' children are four times more as to be out of the schools as compare than those from the wealthiest family 20%. And most of the poorest family forces their children to work and wasting their time school to the school.

Population

There were three primary motivations behind this study on the patterns delinquency among street children in Sindh's District South Karachi. Firstly, the patterns of delinquency among street children in District South Karachi had not been studied before. Second, the number of street children in this

domain, who were delinquent, was on the rise. Thirdly, the street children lacked mutual understanding, which made data collecting challenging and made it a little harder for the researchers to commute to the area. Data from different delinquent activities indicated that there were one hundred street youngsters that made up the study's population.

- i. Only street children was uniformity in the sample
- ii. Street children, who gave their show interest to participate in the study
- iii. Street children who was disconnected from their families
- iv. Children were living in the streets of District South Karachi
- v. Children who were physically and mentally capable of participating in the without any need of immediate medical or psychological interventions

Research Model:

In research model some of major variables would be included like, Poverty, Lack of resources, and lack of Education, how all factors were co-related with the patterns of delinquency among street children.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Table 01: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their Age

AGE IN YEARS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Under 10 years	10	13.9%
10-12 years	20	27.8%
13-15 years	25	34.7%
16-18 years	17	23.6%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The studies findings indicate that the largest proportion of respondents, 34.7%, were between 13-15 years old. This is followed by 27.8% of respondents who were between 10-12 years.

Additionally, 23.6% of respondents were aged 16-18 years, and 13.9% were under 10 years old. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 1: Graphical representation according to their Age.

Table 02: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	72	100%
Female	00	00%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 100%, were male, while 00% were female. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 2: Graphical representation according to their Gender.

Table 03: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their Qualification

QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Less than primary	10	13.9%
Primary	20	27.8%
Middle	15	20.8%
Matric	12	16.7%
Intermediate	8	11.1%
Other	7	9.7%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 27.8%, had a Primary school qualification, followed by 20.8% with a Middle school qualification. Additionally, 16.7% of

respondents had Matriculation, 13.9% had less than Primary education, 11.1% had an Intermediate qualification, and 9.7% had other qualifications. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 3: Graphical representation according to their Qualification.

Table 04: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their qualification before leaving home

QUALIFICATION BEFORE LEAVING HOME	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Less than primary	12	16.7%
Primary	18	25.9%
Middle	20	27.8%
Matric	10	13.9%
Intermediate	6	8.3%
Other	6	8.3%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 27.8%, had a Middle school qualification, followed by 25.9% with a Primary school qualification. Additionally, 16.7% of respondents had less than Primary education, while

13.9% had Matriculation. Both Intermediate and Other qualifications were held by 8.3% of respondents each. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 4: Graphical representation according to their qualification before leaving home.

Table 05: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their faced challenges in education

FACED CHALLENGES IN ACCESSING EDUCATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	45	62.5%
No	27	37.5%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 62.5%, faced challenges in accessing

education, followed by 37.5% who did not face challenges. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 5: Graphical representation according to their faced challenges in education

Table 06: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their Primary Challenge while getting education

PRIMARY CHALLENGES WHILE GETTING EDUCATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Financial difficulties	40	55.6%
Lack of nearby schools	8	11.1%
Health issues	8	11.1%
Family responsibilities	15	20.83%
Other	1	1.4%
Not applicable	0	0.0%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 55.6%, identified financial difficulties as their primary challenge in accessing education, followed by 20.83% who faced family responsibilities. Both lack of nearby schools and health issues were

challenges for 11.1% of respondents each. Only 1.4% cited other challenges, while none of the respondents selected "not applicable." The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 6: Graphical representation according to their Primary Challenge while getting education

Table 07: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their source of income for living on street

TYPE OF SOURCE OF INCOME FOR LIVING ON STREET	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Begging	22	30.6%
Selling items	10	13.9%
Working as cleaner	8	11.1%
Collecting scrap materials	7	9.7%
Street performances	5	6.9%
Working for daily wages	9	12.5%
Involved in illegal activities	11	15.3%
Other	0	0.0%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 30.6%, were engaged in begging, followed by 15.3% who were involved in illegal activities. Selling items accounted for 13.9% of respondents, while 12.5% worked for daily wages.

Additionally, 11.1% worked as cleaners, 9.7% collected scrap materials, and 6.9% participated in street performances. None of the respondents selected "other." The total number of respondents was 64.

Figure 7: Graphical representation according to their source of income for living on street

Table 08: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their father's occupation

FATHER'S OCCUPATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Government service	12	16.7%
Private service	25	34.7%
Jobless	30	41.7%
Business	5	6.9%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 41.7%, had fathers who were jobless, followed by 34.7% whose fathers were in private service. Additionally, 16.7% of respondents had

fathers working in government service, while 6.9% reported their fathers were involved in business. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 8: Graphical representation according to their father's occupation

Table 09: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their household’s monthly income

INCOME IN PKR	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Less than 15,000 PKR	20	27.8%
16,000 - 25,000 PKR	25	34.7%
26,000 - 35,000 PKR	15	20.8%
36,000 - 45,000 PKR	8	11.1%
More than 45,000 PKR	3	4.2%
Not applicable	1	1.4%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 34.7%, had an income between 16,000 and 25,000 PKR, followed by 27.8% with an income of less than 15,000 PKR. Additionally, 20.8% earned between 26,000 and 35,000 PKR, while 11.1%

reported an income between 36,000 and 45,000 PKR. Only 4.2% earned more than 45,000 PKR, and 1.4% indicated that this was not applicable. The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 9: Graphical representation according to their father’s occupation

Table 10: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their family members

FAMILY MEMBERS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
0-1	5	6.9%
2-3	20	27.8%
4-5	42	58.3%
Other	5	6.9%
TOTAL:	72	100%

The study findings indicate that the majority of respondents, 58.3%, had 4-5 family members, followed by 27.8% with 2-3 family members.

Additionally, 6.9% of respondents had 0-1 family members, while another 6.9% selected "other." The total number of respondents was 72.

Figure 10: Graphical representation according to their family members

Summary

The study investigated the “Patterns of Delinquency among Street Children in District South Karachi.” This research focused on understanding the various factors contributing to delinquent behavior among street children, a vulnerable population often exposed to adverse socio-economic conditions. Street children faced unique challenges, including poverty, lack of education, and exposure to violence, which could significantly influence their behavioral patterns. The qualitative research was conducted using an ingeniously developed questionnaire for face-to-face interviews to collect primary data from a sample of 72 street children, drawn from different areas within District South Karachi. The study aimed to examine the diverse social and economic factors influencing delinquent behavior among these children.

The target population for the study was selected due to the rising concerns regarding street children’ delinquency in urban areas and the lack of comprehensive research specifically focused on street children. A sample of 72 street children was identified. A probability sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across different groups and backgrounds. Data were collected through structured interviews with closed-ended questions to facilitate quick, quantifiable, and reliable data elicitation using a self-made questionnaire.

Strict adherence to ethical principles was maintained throughout the research process, including obtaining

informed consent, ensuring participant confidentiality, allowing participants to withdraw at any moment, and conducted interviews in a respectful and supportive manner.

The findings indicate that the largest proportion of respondents (34.7%) was aged 13-15 years, with 58.3% identifying as male. In terms of education, 27.8% had a Primary school qualification, while 27.7% had no formal education. A significant 62.5% faced challenges in accessing education, primarily due to financial difficulties (55.6%). Regarding their activities, 30.6% engaged in begging, and 15.3% were involved in illegal activities.

Family backgrounds indicated that 41.7% of respondents had jobless fathers, and 34.7% reported family incomes between 16,000 and 25,000 PKR. Most respondents (58.3%) had 4-5 family members. Notably, 41.7% left home due to poverty, with 34.7% indicating they left at ages 11-13. The majority (98.6%) had skills before leaving home, with cooking skills being the most common (21.4%). In terms of drug use, 79.2% of respondents reported using drugs, with heroin being the most commonly used substance (29.1%). Many respondents (25.0%) reported obtaining drugs through stealing. Health issues were prevalent, with 34.7% experiencing malnutrition and 25.0% reporting respiratory issues. The majority (34.7%) faced health issues rarely. Additionally, 23.6% were victims of physical violence occasionally, with the perpetrator often unknown (52.8%).

This study highlights the complex interplay of socioeconomic factors contributing to patterns of delinquency among street children in District South Karachi. The findings underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions that address educational access, financial stability, and health care for these vulnerable children.

Limitations

1. It was hard to find street children for the study because they moved around a lot and did not stay in one place for long. Many of them were always searching for food, shelter, or safety, which made it tough to reach them and conduct interviews. This constant movement made it harder to recruit participants and also affected how well the sample represented the broader group.
2. Some of the children who were found didn't want to give permission to participate in the study, which reduced the number of participants and might have limited the variety of responses. Since these children were in a vulnerable situation, many were likely uncomfortable or afraid to share personal information. This hesitation to participate raised ethical concerns and might mean that certain experiences or views were left out of the data.

Conclusion

The patterns of delinquency among street children were a serious problem in District South Karachi that needs to be addressed immediately by legislators, law enforcement, and social services. The results of this study demonstrated the complex relationship between socioeconomic issues—such as poverty, illiteracy, and unstable family dynamics—and delinquent behavior among street children. These factors also had a major impact on the experiences and decisions made by these youngsters. Street children, who were frequently enmeshed in vicious cycles of poverty, confront several difficulties, such as restricted access to healthcare and education, which increases their susceptibility.

The study found that peer pressure, substance misuse, and repeated exposure to violence were major causes of delinquency. A significant percentage of participants acknowledged their drug use, with numerous individuals attributed their circumstances to financial strains and familial disputes. Even if a

sizable portion of these young people were skilled, their options were severely limited by their socioeconomic circumstances and the stigma attached to their status.

Their situation was further made worse by the fact that many of the respondents came from households where there was unemployment. The high rate of drug abuse and involvement in criminal activity highlights the critical need for focused interventions. The results also showed a troubling trend of disengagement from educational institutions, which added to an unbreakable cycle of recidivism.

Implementing comprehensive strategy was necessary to properly address these concerns. This entails strengthening supported networks within families, offering easily accessible career and educational possibilities, and putting policies in place to address peer pressure and drug misuse.

The issue of street delinquency in children in Karachi must be addressed holistically, taking into account the complex interactions between social and economic issues. We might endeavor to lower the rates of juvenile crime and create a safer, more encouraging neighborhood for all children by giving at-risk youth and their families' priority. In the end, these children's well-being was crucial for both their future and the stability and security of society at large.

Recommendations

1. Improving family support networks was essential for tackling the underlying reasons behind street children's delinquency. Many of these children were from unstable or low-income homes, where there might be financial strain and insufficient funds, which could result in abuse or neglect. The creation of community-based initiatives that provided financial aid and counseling can help families get the help they require to establish secure homes.
2. Improving street children's access to education is essential to ending the cycle of crime and poverty. Many of these children have limited resources, or are forced to labor in order to attend school. It is possible to guarantee that street children receive the foundational education required for their growth by establishing free or subsidized educational programs designed especially for them.
3. Improving peer support networks is crucial for encouraging beneficial behaviors among young

people who are at-risk. Peer pressure can have a negative impact on street children and encourage them to engage in delinquent behavior. Peer mentorship programs allow at-risk youth to engage with supportive and guidance-giving role models. As children gain knowledge from their mentors' experiences, these initiatives can foster resilience and sound decision-making.

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